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Studies of ESR Spectra of Some Cu(II) Complexes

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THE esr spectra of copper(II) complexes have been studied by many workers¹⁻⁸. Some of these studies have led to useful conclusion regarding the stereochemistry of Cu(II) in these complexes and the nature of metal-ligand bonding. Detailed esr studies on Cu(II) ion, bonded to oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur atom of the ligand, have been reported^{9,10}. The authors have studied the metal-ligand bond strengths using esr data and the findings are presented here.

Materials and methods :

The copper(II) complexes studied in the present investigation are (i) $\text{Cu}(\text{HMMCO})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and

$\text{Cu}(\text{HBMMCO})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (HMMCO = 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime, HBMMCO = 2'-hydroxy - 3' - bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime); (ii) $\text{Cu}(\text{TMBHA})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (TMBHA = *N*-*m*-tolyl-*p*-methoxy benzohydroxamic acid) and $\text{Cu}(\text{BPPTB})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BPPTB = 4-*S*-benzyl-1-*p*-Cl-phenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret). These complexes were prepared by the methods described earlier²¹⁻²⁴. Electronic spectra, magnetic measurement, conductivity etc. suggest tetragonal symmetry to these complexes²¹⁻²⁴.

The esr spectra of copper(II) complexes of HMMCO and BPPTB were taken at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature in chloroform solution (Fig. 1). ESR spectra of copper(II) complexes of HMMCO, HBMMCO, TMBHA and BPPTB were taken in polycrystalline state at room temperature only (Fig. 2).

The esr spectra of the same copper complexes at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature were obtained from the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, I.I.T., Madras. The esr spectra of some copper complexes at room temperature were also run for us by the E.S.R. Laboratory, I.I.T., Bombay.

Results and Discussion

The esr spectra were analysed by the method of Kneubuhl²⁵, Sands²⁶ and Garman *et al.*¹⁴. The *g* values at room temperature are presented in Table 1 and the hyperfine coupling constants and *g* values at liquid nitrogen temperature are shown in Table 2. The nature of esr spectrum (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) of copper(II) complexes in the present study

Fig. 1

NOTES

Fig. 2

is indicating a tetragonal symmetry²⁷⁻³⁰. This fact supports the observations made on the basis of magnetic and spectral studies²¹⁻²⁴.

TABLE 1—ESR SPECTRA OF POLYCRYSTALLINE COPPER(II) COMPLEXES AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

Copper(II) complexes of	$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	$ g $
HMMCO	2.217	2.049	2.105
HBMMCO	2.241	2.038	2.105
TMBHA	2.255	2.040	2.111
BPPTB	2.214	2.028	2.090

$$|g| = \frac{1}{2}(2g_{\perp} + g_{\parallel})$$

TABLE 2—ESR SPECTRA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES AT ROOM TEMPERATURE AND LIQUID NITROGEN TEMPERATURE IN CHLOROFORM

Copper(II) complexes of	$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	$ g $	$A_{\parallel}$ $10^{-4} \times \text{cm}^{-1}$	$A_{\perp}$	$ A $
HMMCO	2.200	2.041	2.094	163.95	18.73	67.13
BPPTB	2.204	2.035	2.091	168.64	32.79	78.07

$$|A| = \frac{1}{2}(2A_{\perp} + A_{\parallel})$$

Kivelson and Neiman⁵ showed that $g_{\parallel}$ is a moderately sensitive function for indicating covalency; for ionic environment $g_{\parallel}$ is normally > 2.3 , for covalent environment it is < 2.3 . In view of this, covalency of the M-L bond in the present Cu(II) complexes follows the order BPPTB > HMMCO > HBMMCO > TMBHA.

$g_{\perp}$ value of HMMCO and BPPTB in polycrystalline state is nearly the same as that of the value

obtained in chloroform solution. Therefore, it is quite probable that the arrangement of copper(II) ion in polycrystalline state and in chloroform solution may be the same¹⁰. Super hyperfine lines are clearly observed in the esr spectra of HMMCO (in frozen state) in the region between parallel and perpendicular components. This may perhaps come from the nitrogen atom as is observed in some other cases¹. The nature of the σ and π bonds is investigated in the case of Cu(II)-HMMCO and Cu(II)-BPPTB systems where complete data are available (i.e. absorption peaks, $|g|$, $|A|$, $g_{\parallel}$ and $A_{\parallel}$ values). For electronic transitions Table 3 is referred.

TABLE 3—ASSIGNMENT OF THE ELECTRONIC TRANSITION IN CHLOROFORM SOLUTION

Copper(II) complexes of	$E_{xy} \leftarrow E_x 2y^2$ ($B_{1g} \rightarrow B_{2g}$)kK	$E_{yz, zx} \leftarrow E_z 2z^2$ ($B_{1g} \rightarrow E_g$)kK
HMMCO	15.98	17.86
BPPTB	15.62	18.18

Molecular orbital theory put forward by Maki and McGarvey⁴ is used to calculate metal-ligand bond nature. In fact, this theory is strictly applicable to square planar complexes. But many workers³⁰⁻³² applied this theory to complexes having other than square planar structure.

The approximate value of the plane bonding parameter α^2 can be estimated from the following simple expression:

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{|A|}{gK} + \frac{|g| - 2.0023}{K} \quad \dots (I)$$

where, $|A|$ and $|g|$ are average A and g values, p is the free ion dipole term which is given a value of 0.036 cm^{-1} and K is the Fermi contact term which is actually given a value of 0.43.

To obtain in-plane and out-of-plane bonding parameters β^2 and γ^2 respectively, the following simplified expressions were used assuming tetragonal D_{4h} symmetry for Cu(II) in HMMCO and BPPTB complexes¹⁰.

$$g_{||} = 2.0023 - \frac{8\xi\alpha^2\beta^2}{\Delta E(B_{1g} \rightarrow B_{2g})} \quad \dots \text{ (II)}$$

$$g_{\perp} = 2.0023 - \frac{2\xi\alpha^2\beta^2}{\Delta E(B_{1g} \rightarrow E_g)} \quad \dots \text{ (III)}$$

The symbol ξ represents the one electron spin orbit coupling coefficient ($= -828 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The values of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 are set out in Table 4. The bonding parameter α^2 is a measure

TABLE 4—BONDING PARAMETERS OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Copper(II) complexes of	α^2	β^2	γ^2
HMMCO	0.68	0.70	0.68
BPPTB	0.71	0.66	0.51

of the covalency of the plane σ bonding. A value of $\alpha^2 = 1$ indicates complete ionic character while $\alpha^2 = 0.5$ indicates essentially 100% covalent bonding. The β^2 and γ^2 parameters are a measure for covalency in the in-plane and out-of-plane bonding, respectively. β^2 or $\gamma^2 = 1$ indicates no covalent bond and β^2 and $\gamma^2 = 0.5$ corresponds to total covalent character.

The observed value of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 parameters in the present case are indicative of strong in-plane σ and π covalent bonding and out-of-plane π bonding. Out-of-plane covalency character is observed to be more in the BPPTB than in HMMCO complex which may be attributed to the presence of vacant d orbitals in sulphur atom of BPPTB. This favours back π bonding from metal to ligand.

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Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Neodymium(III) Complexes with Mandelic, Cinnamic and Phenylacetic Acids: A Polarographic Study

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MANDELIC, cinnamic and phenylacetic acids were used as complexing agents for metals by different authors¹⁻³. A survey of literature shows that the complexation study of rare earth metal ions with these ligands have not been reported polarographically. In the present paper the authors report the stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of neodymium(III) complexes with mandelic, cinnamic and phenylacetic acid.